

The Triple Division Of The Word, What It Has, And What Is On It

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Abstract

The study deals with the identification of the parts among the Arabic scholars and the modernists, and shows the basis of the classification of these parts of speech in each party. The first party, the Arabic scholars depend on the three - section classification, which are based on two principles namely: the significance and the attribution, unlike the second, who depend in their classifications on several sections, which finishes at seven ones. The research adopted the division of the ancients by means of transmission, and mentality evidence.

Introduction

Almost all grammarians, al-Basri and al-Kfiyun, say that the word in the Arabic language is divided into three categories: noun, verb, and letter (1), but Abu Jaafar Ahmad bin Saber added the fourth chapter called (Caliphate). And the nominative verb means (2). Muhammad bin Ali replied that he (d. 1206 AH) in (his footnote) that the name of the members is not Chapter Four (3). Early grammarians relied on dividing this on two grounds, the first: on (the basis of the signifier and the signified): which is to make the connotation an integral part of the truth of the specific word, which is the choice. It is well known, as in their definition of a noun, that (((denotes a meaning in and of itself is an abstract denotation of conjugation)) (4); the verb ((denotes a conjunction that occurred with time)) (5) and the letter ((which denotes a meaning In other than)) (6) and the other: on the basis of the transmission chain: he says: The word for the individual's pain is to notice the transmission chain. Is it correct or not, then it is the name, and it is correct and do not tell him about it, it is an act, or it is not correct, tell him not that, it is the letter) (7). However, there are observations that grammarians agree or disagree with, including: a. agreeing on the importance of the three temporal verbs. Because when verbs are related to time, as an integral part of their truth, they are present when they are, and absent when they are not, were divided by this observation on (past, present, and future) (8). The verb (victory), for example, has a separate meaning, referring to the past tense. The verb (victory) has an independent meaning, and indicates the present or future tense. The verb (we insist) also has an independent meaning and appears in the present; Performance time in medial is the future (9). Likewise, the data went even on the terms past and present tense, that is: construct (verb, verb), the first: constructive and the other: expressive, but the term present tense is visible, and the call to the kufin (based on a verb), verbs, they have three: (past, present And the permanent) meaning: construct (verb, verb, subject) (10), and for Makhzumi (past, present, command, and permanent) (11), and the latter is the verb, meaning and use, and in most of its uses it refers to the continuation and continuation of the event (12), if The operator was (13), which is an example of (the subject), so what happens? About describing her decisions, towards: (Asas, Mahmoud, Karim, Hassan), and it is called when Basrain b (the name of the actor). B- The difference in doing that, so the visionary considers it as a basis, as a narrow one from the past and present tenses, and it is derived from it, and the present tense is derived from the past, and the Cuffs have endorsed it as expressive. , And from the literal present tense, and a branch of it because its origin (verb), the lam and the verse were removed; for repeated use, the hamza increased the pronunciation of the consonant, indicating a contradiction to the receptor of the tense verb (14). The research concluded that the permanent verb spoken by Al-Kufi and Al-Maqsoumi is not a fact, but rather a name Belhaz: a derivation derived from the tense of the present and the verb, and the appropriate time. For similarity between them (15), it is the strongest noun in the action after the verb; it works internally, not externally.

By accepting the five formal noun marks, namely: preposition, tanning, appeal and support (16). The construction and formula buildings (representative) are not a work, but the name of the buildings; because his credibility and longevity reveal his name, not his truth. The verbs denote alpha-linen movements, not the verbs

of Fa-Lin, the movement does not remain twice, which indicates the permanent invalidity of what has already been said by the Cuffs and Makzoomi (17). In the sense of verbs indicating a karmic action, killing and striking, and this movement cannot remain two times indicating that the form (permanent verb) does not count on verbs, it is a form of noun forms. C- The time of the (permanent) verb and its action in the other when the kufic caused it to be a verb bearing a charge, that is: time and action, because they do not go out from the nominative to the actual; Because of the time he spent in erasing J gives the indications of ossification outside the reality of the original, the mother of his work is because he escaped p from the origin, and its derivatives; So called Albesrion (representative noun), the acceptance of the noun clearly indicates the formal noun surrounding the active case of being displaying the behavior of the present tense verb.

H Amara (Active) When the Kofis prove steadfastness and constancy, he works for him the originality of our saying: (I am the writer of a letter) that is, about three times if I said: (I am the writer of the message), I honor continuity and continuity in the peculiarities of the past tense, and his entry into the (Chapter of Addition) This reveals his lack of clarity in reality. It's a name on her face. Tonween, attribution, and add. X does not apply verb signs to the building (P Ely), namely: (Ta), (No), (Request), or (ABC Anette) (18), other than. Name cards that indicate that you are not indicating that it was flat. D. The functions of the grammatical act its occurrence, that is: a calendar that has no famine, that is: it is not evaluated in the words of the mayor, so it is a combination of him and him, and the case that the building (subject) is calculated on the second is not an elevation, towards our saying: (Did Muhammad write the lesson?), Or (Lesson Writer?). R: The saying of a constructive peasant (representative), as the Coffins claim, leads to saying that the source is also a permanent act; Being ((He does his work in the past and others)) (19): (Your brother's abandonment of you is an injustice), that is, he does his work of transgression, indicating its continuation. The event and its continuation in the past, present and future in one symptom, which is the heir. The upshot is that the construct (subject) is a noun, not a verb.

Mahdi Makhzoumi's opinion in the form (verb)

Makhzoumi believes that a form (verb) - in the larger sense - is not a verb in reality. Not assigning time and evaluators to the fact that the verb, because the verb identifies two things: the first, is related to giving indications of time, and the second: it is based on it and attributes it to it and carries it, and it is constructed (I do) in the absence of these two features, there is no evidence for its time, as there is no Transmission chain in it. Because its form indicates only verb request, there is no verb, no time the subject becomes truly obsessed, in addition to the absence of attribution. It indicates that a thousand Al has been assigned, i.e. (Monday), or (F group), or (J Salutation), (N women), or (hidden pronoun) are not nouns, nor pronouns, as the grammarians claim, but they are Pseudonym letters indicate the gender or number of the recipient, according to Makhzoumi claim (20). The outcome of his speech: Free (equivalent to what I do) on the importance of the princess of time and her support, and the necessary is to get out of the actual; The absence of the aforementioned two strings, but it is in line with the past and present (verb) forms of (verb)

Muhammad Baqir Al-Sadr's response to Al-Makhzoumi

Sayyid Muhammad Baqir al-Sadr (d. 1400) answered, in this word al-maqzumi, saying: The event is relative to an actor available in the form (I do), and is also available in the past tense and the present tense, but it is noted where the past tense verification and information, and in the issue of resurrection and transmission, which The sentence descends from warning to creation, without affecting the meaning of the verb; The fact that the reference in the formula is deemed worthy is not checked outside but in the realm of reason (21). The difference between the two views is that al-Makzumi denies the significance of the form (I do) in (time and support), and the crisis is the actual absence of them, but when Sayyid al-Sadr does not negate the significance of the form (I do) on the actual chain of transmission, but it is proven with the two previous brothers and the present tense. Because some of the verb of the chain of transmission is a syllabary and the truth of the component, but the reference in the formula was not achieved after the first predicate in (I do), but that al-Sadr denied the entry of time in the fact that all the verbs are identical or that. Contained, but understood through Azamiya (22), in contrast to Makhzoumi, who denied his time without his two brothers. It seems that the phrase al-Makzumi: a free equation (I do) on the meaning of the princess, realist and predicate, and temporal at the same time, away from the sayings of righteousness for four reasons:

1. The formula (I do) as a general concept and multi Bmassadagaha, towards: (read, you win, arrived) , for example, are the actions of the meaning of the request verb include (event), ie: (reading, Zakat, and prayer) of the student (Commanding), And emotion from what is required of him (the assigned), by means of the request (the verb)
2. If we prove the existence of an event issued by an updated, Del Palmlazemh on the attribution which binds to the predicate (verb) to Musnad (actor):(As the hadith and attribution are the spirit of the verb that is between its sides, and is this but the meaning of the verb?
3. The actual proven formula Bakdia in significance to the issuance of an event of an actor what or already characterized by the, shows beyond any doubt on the significance of the time, as what happened done by an updated, or characterized by, but has a timeless collector, whether It was in past, present, or future time.

4. if Tenslna, and we said: that the assigned marks of this formula are letters, not Dmair, but the purpose of determining the sex of beyond, in terms of the number or type, is itself a presumption that beyond an actor, and datum him the truth, about our saying: (books Zaidan ,(or (they wrote Zidon ,(or (Ketbn Hindat), Valvaal in these sentences is the name of the apparent ;For every verb is a subject - whether outwardly or concealed - indicating that the form of (do) is a verb ;The event and the attribution, as well as time, and these are parts of any grammatical verb.

Here, we ask Al-Makhzoumi: If the form (do) is not a verb as he says, is it a noun or a letter? Saying in the name of the model (do) does not stand up to criticism, for reasons such as: Not building in favor of the names because they imitate a certified form (I do) .b He does not apply the five cards to its members. The name is simple and light. Because his name is one and there is no second, and the verb is called heavy (23); it is a compound of event, subject, and time, but the form is of the gender of the second, meaning: the verb, not the first, i.e. the noun. The noun is characterized by constancy and permanence, and the verb occurs and renews (24), and the formula here fits the second and not the first. To transcend itself over the other isnad (25); since it pulses in action with the origin of its position, it denotes a (verb) verb, not a noun. And if it was said: The shape is calculated on the letters, then it is formed by evidence of them: a. read), for example, indicate the meaning, even if we say: free of time and support, but it is a function of the event (reading), indicating that it is a verb and not a letter. Independent concepts until their meaning is achieved, and the case (reads) is, for example, separate and stand-alone; since the so-called WinPE I animation, found in bulk installations, this is the business case. V Applicability of the quote to construct (I do), ie: Important upon request, acceptance of J Salutation (26), Flat proof, and no. All Gh's words when he limited them to three, were confined to the previous Belhaz by standards, as it was famous, as well as with temporal verbs with their three movements, and whenever he answered him, this indicates that the formula (I do) is in fact no, and even if we say: If the intention was from That (doing) as a general concept, it is also related to the action of buildings. This is all about the sayings of the ancient Arabs that are divided by word, whether it is divided on the basis of the signifier and the signified, or on the basis of the chain of transmission, with the most prominent problems mentioned by some modern scholars who are divided on this, and all of them took the research news.

All the position of scientists GH modern of dividing floor triple

Contemporary scholars divided the ancient triple word but invented new words, and c for these advanced innovations related to reality through the noun, friendliness, and verb, respectively; because they believed that the early grammatical limit for these sections was not comprehensive. The most famous of these sections:

- First: The quartet committee divided Dr. Anis Ibrahim (27) on the basis of (structure, meaning, position) into: (name, pronoun, work, tool)
- Second: Dr. Mahdi Makhzoumi's last four-wheel drive team (28) without proving accountability for: (noun, nouns (29), verb, instrument), where he used the adjective, verb noun, auditors. .
- Third: The quintet division of Dr. Mustafa Jamal al-Din (30) on the basis of (meaning, form, structure, function) into: (name, description, metonymy, verb, letter)
- Fourth: Dividing the seventh by Dr. Tamam Hassan (31) on the basis of (construction, meaning) into: (noun, state (32), pronoun, successor (33), adverb, verb, and). (the tool)

The modernist argument in response to the schism of the ancients:

Among the most prominent arguments of scholars who suffered from the events of the ancient division:

A- The words of the ancients: The restriction of the name (as Maan Zaid in himself) is not documented with a comprehensive name Because he found many words in the language that do not have this modification, the phases do not tell us the meaning present in the same autonomy, despite being a noun overt, as in nouns (metaphors, and conjugations), such as pronouns, related nouns, references, and nouns of verbs of all kinds. Three - does not denote a specific noun, in addition to its non-acceptance of official noun marks, such as (preposition, tanween, nuna, isnad, isnad.), And for this they presented these two mentioned sections, so that the word division consists of five (34), not three, They are: (noun, metonymy, caliphate, verb, and letter). Words facing the name of the value, and inside it, including the meaning of the verb, that is, they indicate the meaning of the verb. Do these words put nouns in the field or are they verbs? How the parsing is directed? As is the case in (Khafalif and Descriptions) from our saying: (Al-Halat is lazy), so his appearance is a noun, even if it is related to one building movement and inside it is a past tense. The meaning is (after), and as we say: (Ali wrote the lesson, and the writer, and the name is similar; to accept the name cards, and the esoteric inclusion of a thousand families, which is: (he writes), and this is what prompted the modernists to make these two members and other parts of the word (35).

V The narrators noticed some words that included the partial verb, namely: (time), the names of the promised, k (conditions); Because when the ancients knew the name, they said that (on the meaning of what is shown in the same denotation of the association's inventory), in At tz them, b (day), and (night), for example; In order to denote time as a part and not a condition, they created a new part of the word, which is (the adverb) (36). W Arab scholars see an origin in the word to be placed as one, which is the origin, as in the solid state, but the modernists have found and placed Budan words, as in (verbs), meaning the actual derivatives, and

(descriptions), that is: (descriptive derivatives) towards: For example, when his material is placed in one place, it is an indication of the event, and its form is placed in another place, which is the ratio of the event to a representative in a complete proportion, and this means that the position in these descriptions is not real. And because it is contrary to the original, it was necessary for them to rely on another mind that divides the overlapping patterns, so they created this data derived from another section of the most shared word, which is prince (description) (37), in order to distinguish it from (verb) Thread Bodaan also with the difference being that the first is a noun and the other is a verb.

C - A form of narrators on the yin criterion, which is the n that was adopted by the ancients in dividing the word, i.e. (based on the signifier and the signified), and (based on the authenticity of the chain of transmission), i.e. Because they say the first rule: the word sign in its meaning either denotes the meaning of Z in itself or not, and the second letter, and the first is either accompanied by a means at some point, so it is a verb, or not. It is the noun, and this division makes the word not indicate the meaning of independence limited to the letter, meaning that the letter does not indicate its meaning in itself, then they said: Where do we put these names: (pronoun, noun and noun)? And the like, do we put them together with names that indicate their meaning independently or with letters? This ambiguity does not indicate its meaning independently, as it is like the case of letters in the lack of others in revealing its meaning, and this is the reason for making the division of the word four, not three, according to the authors of this saying. Think, as is the case with the chain of transmission, meaning that the word - from hadiths - either falls into a chain of transmission. Or attributed to him, or attributed to him and attributed to him, or he has no attribution or attributed to him, the first: the verb, the second: the continuous pronoun, the third: the noun, and the fourth: the letter, this division makes the parts of the word four, not three (38)

H- We notice the presence of some narrators and the presence of some corner words found at the ends of the cross in their meaning of the meaning of independence, like most words of the language, and others are not, like Harouf of all kinds, towards: (in, l, al) for example, or some of the names of the terms of his raising are not Independent by itself, towards: (if, when, Ian) as well as interrogative and conditional nouns and the like in their lack of a comment for that, they created the term (tool) that combines letters, adverbs, inquiries, and conditions under one name, as one of the word splitters, as the comments links This is not a corner of the sentence, but rather a limited function. To intertwine parts of speech until the full meaning is achieved by linking speech with the other. And every tool that relates the parts of speech to each other and explains them is called the term (instrument) between hadiths, as in Tamam Hassan (39), Ibrahim Anees (40), and al-Makhzoumi (41), or the term (the letter) as in Mr. Mustafa Jamal al-Din (42).

If only my hair's and they relied on the division of the ancient,for E .proposals several

The first hypothesis: the hadiths claim that the term noun condition in the ancients, i.e. (indicating a meaning in itself) has not been verified in names (metaphors), for example, is a word that is not accurate. Because some noun signs are suitable for application to metaphorical nouns, such as the transmission string, as in our saying: (He is a scholar), or the preposition, as in our saying: (He has knowledge). Or the call, as in our saying: (Oh this). As for non-acceptance (definition, and tanween, the reason is not in the possibility, but in the impediment, which is the construction, this first, and secondly, we find the significance of (metaphors) in its meaning through its references that it denotes it, that is, it is the source of the apparent name, as in our saying: (Zaid respects you), where the pronoun is (enough). It is concerned with affirmation and support, meaning the division of the three Arab scholars. It was a center that does not deviate from the name, verb and letter, until the problem of Dr. Taha rushes Hassan to the two forms of exclamation (what I do and do) which he calls (the contradiction of exclamation), which are the forms of praise and slander (yes) and slander. He called it (The Caliphate of Praise and Slander) (43) this is due to the structures and not to the vocabulary. It is not permissible to deal with these formulas as individual expressions, and then judge their parts - once they are combined - as nouns or verbs. These structures were present among Arab scholars. , But the concentration of their difference in its derivation or stagnation, as in the contradiction of arrogance. Or how to direct it in Arabic, as in the succession of exclamation - in its two forms - is it a form of Media forms or a form of authorship? Determining the quality of each form is sufficient to determine the grammatical direction of each, and we did not see them allocate a fourth section added to the division of words in Arabic, as contemporary scholars said. Pain prompted him not to make (idioms) a widespread meaning in another section of the floor, as long as he was apt to enter under the name section.

The second hypothesis: the rule of the ancients is that the word is a noun or verb, which was outwardly and not inwardly, as in their judgment on (nominal verbs) associated with a single building movement, so its appearance is the noun, and inside it is a verb, and this suffices in counting it from the three sections of the word, i.e. members The name by which the SPI is chosen in its surroundings, as noted in the opening of the research is that its collateral movement expresses a single mind to accept its name cards B- Evidence for what the old said: The nouns of verbs do not indicate this by an unspecified statement other than the definition (44), that is, the apparent meaning between their knowledge n repetition. Because the origin of nouns is as in (adverbs, or diamond dir), or letters, as in (prepositions) NAPT Mnab verbs, meaning not rude (45), and this speech is

similar to the words of grammarians: the origin of nouns to express them, in construction works (46) That is, to judge the type of word in the Arabic language, it appears in many cases. Likewise, words are said with (adjectives) and (metaphors), the name of Zahrahmy And because they accepted his signs in many of them, scholars of the Arabic language when judging the sections of Arabic discourse, their judgment was focused on the appearance of the word, by referring to its formal signs that are at its beginning, as in (definition).) In the noun, or (the letters annit), and (not) in the verb, or it is in the latest, as in (special characters) in the noun, or (J Salutation) to do so; otherwise it is diffused (47).

The third hypothesis: that (day and night), for example, is definitely one of the names. For their acceptance of noun marks, despite the meaning of that time contained, this does not mean that they came out of the harem of the names M section of a new word, which is (adverb); Because it indicates the meaning of a certain thing. As for the mention of time in these two, it is not a constraint that assesses their truth, but rather a constraint that determines the truth of the action. With it because adverbs count for nouns, not verbs; The fact that the criterion of the noun applies to them, in addition to the fact that the verb is from within the verb itself, that is, from the weight of the form (the verb) and its sisters, in contrast to the adverbs of time. It is the pronunciation of any of the essence of its letters.

The fourth hypothesis: the presence of some of the advanced words in formulas, and the subtraction of the material, and others that are the first in nominal and verbal such as the derivative does not mean the overlapping of positions between the two cases as the narrators claim Because the subject of the verb in the word - here - is the acceptance of the nominal signs, so it is a noun, as in the description, or the acceptance of verb signs, so it is a verb, as in the verb, so the words: (zaid), (door) and (tree), and (Asad) They put one, and accepted name cards, and the words: (lesson, science, ladar s, schools), Boudan is put, including her. Acceptance of name cards as in (schools), or acceptance of verb signs as in the first three verbs, and this distinction separates the meanings of nouns and verbs, and there is no justification for entering another section called (adjective or adjective), which includes nouns placed in two modes, towards: (The subject's name, the subject, the accusative adjective), and the like, and make it part of her noun word (adjective)

The fifth thesis: There is a clear overlap in the parts of the word among contemporary scholars, as in (pronoun, metonymy, adjective, and caliphate). Ibrahim Anis and Tamam Hasan made (the pronoun) an independent division of the word divisions, including (pronouns, noun, noun) and the number) (48). As for Al-Makhzoumi, he made it from believing in the noun (a metaphor), which includes (pronouns, noun and sign noun, conjunction, interrogation, and subjunctive) (49), and Dr. Mustafa Jamal. Religion increased (verb nouns) (50) The same is the case with (adjective) or (description), so Ibrahim Anees made it one of the testimonies that bear the name (51), unlike Makhzoumi who made it a verb, and called it (the permanent verb). It is the choice of the kufic school. The verb means content and time (52), and the same words are said with (the successor) with their validation with the goodness of Dah. Surat Al-Din (55) is perplexed and disagreed with it. The lack of a common collector that brings it together, it is a mrd Aqa.

The sixth thesis: Establishing a new section, which is (the tool) or (tools) to include everything that preserves the words of the language, Dr. Ibrahim Anees says, whether the letters are about: (letters) from exile), (preposition), (kindness) and (exception) And the like, or nouns, towards: (interrogative and conditional nouns), and (adverbs of time and place), or verbs towards: (exclamation formulas)) as said by Dr. Ibrahim Anis (56 years old) and Dr. Makhzoumi (57), and his circle may expand To include the transcription verbs, towards: (Kan and her sisters), and (Kad and her sisters) as Dr. Hassan presented (58), but Dr. Mustafa Jamal al-Din restricted (the tool) to (the letter), meaning: (the letters of meanings) (59), and made the name consistent with the term letter. Famous as if he equated them with concept and validity. In fact, there is no need for this action as long as the triple division is appropriate.

It seems that the words of the modern scholars - this - do not escape the wound .Because there is a big difference between the letters of the meanings that do not indicate any meaning in themselves, such as (Ba), for example, and are counted from the validators of the tools, and between interrogative names and the condition, for example, and are counted as well from them in (who, what, when, and where) For example, in reality denotes a meaning because they nicknamed them for the singular sane name, or sane, or time and place , and so with the names of the condition, the former does not indicate the meaning in itself ;For that function but be as the t duck between the ends, towards our saying: (as decided by the pen ,(unlike the other a t be function as a link with another party, about our saying: (from come to you .(?The same words are said with (verbs of exclamation) and (abrogative verbs), so these are considered verbs .Because it is itself it denotes a meaning, that is, the state of its being singular ;Because the research mentioned that dividing the triple word revolves around the orbit of the individuation, not the structure, i.e. (the signifier and the signified), so we said: (How beautiful is the spring), if we looked at the word (more beautiful) by what it is singular - we would judge its effect .Being located on a form of the past tense, which is a form of (verb), unlike our looking at it which is based on a form of exclamation.

The same words also said with Duplicator acts, towards: (became, and has become) , for example, as the first act shows the occurrence of the time in the morning, and the other shows that it occurs in the evening, with

Dalalthma on needful in the past, but this speech is different. If it falls into a specific structure, as if we said: (The atmosphere has become beautiful), then the verb (has become) - here - unless it is attached to its two ends, does not indicate a complete meaning, unless it fulfills them, i.e. Valal of here is not in the executable, but Palmqtadha; The verb denotes the meaning of the state of being singular, but what is required of the composition is an impediment to its meaning unless it completes its parts through which good silence is achieved, and this is the state of tools in its broad sense among the modernists.

The seventh hypothesis: The difference in the basis of division leads - without doubt - to a difference in the division of the word. The ancients relied on two foundations in their division of the word, namely (the signifier and the signified) and (the validity of the transmission chain). On the basic principles of the ancients, as in (meaning, function, significance, formulation, structure, structure and meaning). It seems that the hadiths in this work confuse the morphological function with the grammatical function, so that the position of the word and the playing of the grammatical function are the product of fixation, and the case is that the ancients began to see the morphological (lexical) function. Knowledge of central importance, and talking about context and structure - on which the modernists relied will lead to the creation of other departments, as in (Job and Training), because they are two contextual functions, and this is what left them mixed with formulas (exclamation, praise and slander), for example, where they rule. On these formats configuration cylinders. If their judgment was on the singular form, they would cease from the rulings of the request.

The eighth thesis: the famous narration transmitted by the glass in labor, and it is from the words of the Commander of the Faithful Ali, may God bless him and grant him peace, addressing the father of the Black Dallah (d.69 AH). It works as a movement foretelling the named movement, and the letter foretells the meaning, and in the name it does not, and I know my father Aswad that the names of the three are: apparent, implicit, not apparent in meaning, nor implicit. But scholars differ in knowing what is neither apparent nor implicit. (60). Perhaps what is extracted from the content of this novel carries the following connotations:

A- The Imam (may God bless him and grant him peace) confined the chapters of speech to the three, in terms of the rational division that limited the components of speech, and restricted it to two limits, one of which is the citizen: it indicates the complete absence of the gathering of his members, as in his saying: (all speech), and the second of them By (ethical acknowledgment), with the assumption (all of that) indicating understanding and understanding of all members. Speech and the imam did not specify the speech in Arabic, but left him to divorce it. As if it indicates its presence in several languages, says Al-Zij (61), and Abu Al-Barakat bin Al-Anbari (62)

B - The imam, may God bless him and grant him peace, made the basis of division a sign of the signifier and the signified, meaning the name and title, and this means that the three sections do not deviate from this principle.

He, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, made a statement of its meaning, money from his illness, and descended and (its essence) from a pronoun related to a surah, and a naphtha in the appearance of the name and (its meaning). The names of the question, a condition and a sign, are related, and all that is referred to by an ambiguous name - this does not deviate from the name of the certificates in the faculty, and it is in itself evidence of the sincerity of what the ancients went to in terms of limiting linguistic words to the triple division only.

W The standard differentiation of the Imam, May God bless him and grant him peace, between scholars is knowledge of what is neither apparent nor implicit. Because it is on layers, just like talking on layers, and this means that determining the final meaning, meaning: (neither explicit nor implicit), makes it difficult for the common people to reveal its truth and understand its name, because it requires more knowledge. . From the words of the Arabs and their conditions. Taking into account the context of the speech and the situation of the callers; And because it represents a deep depth in the bowels of meaning, it is difficult to know its depth, so no one would think of the meaning of this section, as the name appears in the first note, meaning the short meaning, the adverb. Adverb that refers to a comprehensive meaning of its multiple individuals, including sign names, pronouns, conjugations, interrogative names, conditional nouns, and the like. This interpretation indicates a differentiation between the scholars. Because the meanings of this section are neither explicit nor implicit. The fact that the first (apparent noun) and second (implicit noun) are known to the general public, in contrast to the third (vague name); It is a field in which linguists and linguists compete, as is - in fact - contemporary learners.

Even if we say that there is some noticeable in some sections of the word, it is possible to respond to its origins in response to a million beauties without introducing other sections, as SPI did with (the successor), which made Abu Jaafar the grammatical section. The fourth topic of the word sections denied that, as he made it one of the members of The Name, indicating that this division is (mental) or (inductive). As the difference between the two is that the first ((the mind refrains from another division, as a developed division, and the division mentality only if the exile and the evidence is the dual division)) (63), and the other is that (()) ..the mind does not give up its final imposition. But remember the fact that the divisions learned to extrapolate, which is the division of the monotheistic religions into: Judaism, Christianity and Islam. (64) As for his mental entity, it is the saying of Abu Al-Barakat bin Al-Anbari (d. 577 AH): ((Because we found these three sections express everything that comes to pass) In the mind, and delusions in the imagination even if there is)) - here - a fourth part in which something remains in the soul. You see that if one of these three parts falls, then something remains in the self

that cannot be expressed, and faces what has fallen, and when these sections are through the whole, matters indicate that it is not only these three parts)) (65); Because the word either indicates a meaning or it does not indicate, and the first: Either it indicates a meaning in itself or in something else, and if it indicates a meaning in another, then it is the letter, and if it indicates a meaning. By itself, it either indicates its temporal structure or not. The first: is the verb, and the second: is the noun (66), and this is the binary division that revolves around the orbit of negation and affirmation, meaning that the mental division is confined to these parts specifically, and this means that the meanings are only three, either they denote the subject, the noun, or An event and time with a verb, or on a link between the event and the topic. (67) as for my Hittite; There are four reasons:

- The first: ((Art scholars followed the words of the Arabs, and found only three types, and if there was a fourth type, they would have found something from it)) (68)
- The second: Arabic terms that were not translated or translated as the Orientalist (Wright) says (69)
- Third: Logicians and the origins of the yen agree on dividing the triple word (name, word, and instrument) (70) starting from Aristotle (about 322 BC) and up to the present day, meaning (word, tool).): The verb, a letter in the terminology of the grammatical people, as in the first, or in the noun, and the verb and the letter, as in the second (71), indicating that this division is triple, only.
- Fourth: The tripartite division of the word and its borders is at the core of Arab and Islamic culture, and is not imported. This is also evidenced by the saying of Sheikh Al-Naini (p. 1355 AH): ((The reason for this trinity is from the words of the Commander of the Faithful (may God's prayers and peace be upon him), and not from the words of the Commander of the Faithful. ” (72). In conclusion, this phrase suffices to respond to those who claim that the origin of the tripartite division is Greek (73), and that it is pure Arabic (74).

Conclusion

This is the saying about the division of the word according to the following Arabic scholars and modernists:

1. The well-known agreement to divide the word according to a noun, verb, and letter, and the basis for this division was to notice the signifier and the signified, or to have the attribution, by virtue of reason and induction, and some of them added a fourth section, which is (the Caliphate).
2. The well-known agreement to divide the verb on past, present, and matter, as according to the Basra, or on past, present, and permanent, as among the Kufis.
3. The modern scholars divided the word into four sections, as according to Dr. Ibrahim Anis and Mahdi al-Makhzoumi, or into five sections, as according to Dr. Mustafa Jamal al-Din, or into seven sections, as according to Dr. Tammam Hassan. The most prominent of their newly developed divisions are: (pronoun, adjective, metonyms, succession, and tool). My well-known basis for their tripartite division of the word divider, that is, it refers in reality to (significance) and (chain of transmission).
4. This tripartite division is at the core of the Arab and Islamic culture, and is not imported from other cultures, such as the Greek, for example.

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